

METUVERSE

(Metaverse Campus of Middle East Technical University)

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Abstract

METUVERSE (Middle East Technical University Universe) is an academic and realistic metaverse Campus of Middle East Technical University (METU). Its name has coined the combination of the university name “METU” and “Verse” denoting the universe. The project is modeling an academic, administrative, cultural, and social environment by solving three major problems (distance learning-communication, verification of academic documents, and protection.)

With this project, the university structures and environment have been started to be modeled in a virtual environment parallel to its chronological historical development. The architectural plans, photos, campus land afforestation reports, and academic publications on campus development have been collected from affiliated units in the university. The first department of the campus, the Faculty of Architecture, was modeled, and users may visit the model with personal computers or virtual reality glasses. Besides, the project is developed only by university components.

Keywords: metaverse, virtual reality, building information modeling, blockchain.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Metaverse

Neal Stephenson coined the Metaverse term in his science fiction novel Snow Crash in 1992 [1]. The term is a combination of “meta” and the stem “verse” from the word “universe.” It illustrates an independent virtual world where avatars can interact with each other and where users can do everything but their basic life needs by using virtual reality (VR) glasses connected to computers with cable. Thus, the adventure of humanity to create a new universe in the virtual environment began under the leadership of this world. The

post-reality universe is a continuously existing multi-user environment that combines physical reality and digital virtuality [2]. It is built on the convergence of technologies that provide multimodal interactions with digital items, people, and virtual surroundings [2]. As a result, the metaverse is a network of enduring multi-user socially networked immersive experiences [2].

1.1.1. History of Metaverse

In the past 30 years, even the first imagined universe could not be created due to the inadequacy of technology, but the meaning of the current term has become increasingly widespread. There are some critical peri-

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Figure 1: Brief Timeline of the Metaverse Development [3]

ods in developing the term in history, such as the birth of the Internet, virtual reality (VR) glasses launching, and blockchain technology.

Duan et. Al. “Metaverse for Social Good: A University Campus Prototype” [3] states that there is no exact equivalent of the ideal metaverse, but some great metaverse forerunners are illustrated in a brief timeline, as shown in Figure 1.

In addition, the last step of this period is the “Coronavirus disease 2019” pandemic. The course of the pandemic has changed the view on the digital world, especially the metaverse. According to Kerdvibulvech [4], COVID-19 has impacted the creation of reality-based technologies (virtual and augmented reality) and the metaverse. In a previous study, Kerdvibulvech [5] emphasized the future of location-based augmented reality systems and games such as Pokémon GO. Technology companies are increasing research and development investments in online communication due to the need and demand.

1.1.2. Development of Metaverse

The realization of the term in today’s meaning depends on completing some interrelated features. The concept has been linked to the development led by the gaming industry and inspired the massively multiplayer online video games and decentralized virtual world projects. It will come to life with the realization of augmented reality, Artificial Intelligence (AI) agents, Web 3.0, and blockchain technological developments.

In addition, many other industries could be enhanced with the metaverse in the sense of economy and an equal world. According to Dwivedi et al. [6], marketing, tourism, leisure and hospitality, citizen-go-

vernment engagement, health, education, and social networks are just a few industries that could drastically change if organizations were to adjust their business models and operational capabilities to operate in the metaverse. Moreover, the metaverse can be a first step to closing the gap for disability groups. As Seigneur and Choukou [7] state, the awareness it creates and the destruction of the limits of real life.

Furthermore, the research mentioned that although the metaverse is mainly related to virtual or augmented reality, more than developing these technologies is needed to achieve success. For an ideal metaverse, multimedia technologies must ensure that the digital economy is transparent, stable, and sustainable. Blockchain-related technology is necessary because it is decentralized, that is, peer-to-peer. From this perspective, this coding system can store economic figures and essential data securely. S. Nakamoto [8] mentioned that a peer-to-peer network using proof of work is reliable and safe from a possible attack on the data because honest nodes controlled by a majority of the hardware system of the computers work the verification and storage of information.

It is mentioned for an electronic cash system, but S. Nakamoto mentioned that this consensus mechanism could be utilized for any needed rules and incentives.

Technology companies develop custom metaverses related to their visions, and there is no connection between the projects. Today, video games are more realistic than the graphic quality of these projects. Projects similar to the metaverse are defined as works of some of these custom metaverse projects made by tech companies are a community-driven platform where creators can monetize voxel ASSETS and gaming experiences

on the blockchain [9]. Another example is Roblox, which is building the tools and platform that empower people to create their own immersive experiences so that any world they can imagine can be brought to life [10]. Game companies update their games to turn the project into a game, while technology

companies are creating their metaverse systems as a game. As a third part, universities research and develop the technological background of the metaverse and metaverse-related terms.

1.1.3. Previous Studies and Projects

One of the first articles about the issue states that some fundamental elements of the metaverse exist for it to function [11]. “These are realism (allowing users to feel fully immersed in an alternate realm), ubiquity (enabling access to the system via all existing digital devices and maintaining the user’s virtual identity throughout all system transitions), interoperability (enabling the creation and movement of 3D objects anywhere and allowing users to have seamless, uninterrupted movement throughout the system), and scalability (enabling the efficient concurrent use of the system by large numbers of users)” [11]. Another article interviewed 624 experts on their thoughts on the metaverse in 2040, and more than half of the experts believe that it will be in our daily lives for social, educational, governmental, and economic purposes [12]. One of the experts in the article, Aymar Jean Christian, states that it has the potential to shift the power dynamics with effective policies made by the ones who are developing it, suggesting a potentially more equal world [12]. Even though some experts believe that the metaverse can only reach its potential by having a real-world to “escape from,” our project is perceived as a “helper” and “developer” to more opportunities that are created for the university components.

Figure 2: MetaHKUST view [13]

However, the current technology required to realize the metaverse concept is insufficient. It is necessary to conduct research and development in universities to develop metaverse-related technologies. Some universities have started to work since last year and have been involved in the process by making their metaverse campus projects. According to the news published by NFTEVENING [13], Hong Kong University started building the world’s first metaverse campus, MetaHKUST. The university plans to open the world’s first physical-digital twin campuses, Hong Kong University’s new Guangzhou campus [13]. MetaHKUST is considering blockchain-secured diplomas or transcripts awarded as NFTs, and the members may create NFTs, tokens, or digital art in its long-term plan [13]. MetaHKUST attaches importance to modeling by adhering to reality, and the metaverse campus view of the project is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

According to the news-mentioned figures, Pan Hui, who is a professor of the Computational Media and Art Department at Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (HKUST), said that [13].

“Using Zoom feels like you’re just looking at a 2D screen. But through virtual reality, you can feel as if you’re there. I think interaction is very important for learning. How you interact with students around you will increase your learning outcome.”

Another metaverse campus project is “Ifland,” created by SK Telecom and collaborated with Korea University [14]. Korean University’s metaverse campus was created, including the School’s Main Gate, Central Plaza, Main Building, Hosang (Tiger Statue), SK Future Hall, Main Auditorium, etc. Each member of the university can use the system for various academic calendars, such as lectures, group assignments, university fes-

Figure 3: MetaHKUST view [13]

Figure 4: IFLAND view [14]

tivals, and entrance and graduation ceremonies [14]. Ifland, the metaverse campus view of Korea University, is shown in Figure 4.

Today, there are a few metaverse campus projects around the world. METUVERSE is the first metaverse campus in Turkey. For an ideal metaverse, the whole metaverse campus projects should merge and take place in a single universe from an academic metaverse perspective.

1.2. Metuverse

Considering the literature and previous projects, our project is crucial for education and social networks since we are looking from a real campus point of view, accepting the needs and demands of students, teachers, workers, and anyone who has or had a relation with METU in the campus as a whole. Educational activities suffered greatly during the pandemic around the world. The student had to contact only academicians with two-dimensional camera connections during the lectures, which negatively affected the education quality. According to Mystakidis [2], 2D education has some negative limitations that impact the education quality, such as low self-perception, no presence, inactivity, and crude emotional expression. In this step, the “metaverse” term has the potential of a solution and interaction opportunity that will make all online education and communications more effective. Thus, the term has become important not only in the game industry but also in every sector that requires communication and has become one of the words we use daily. Our project involves many of the metaverse terminologies, such as Extended reality (XR), Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR). However, it fits into one of the best terminologies, mirror worlds. Mirror worlds are digital

Figure 5: Metuverse Cobblestone Texture [17]

creations replicating the social and physical aspects of the natural world in a virtual reality environment, mapped to the real world [12]. For example, these can be real-world stadiums, museums, and, in our case, a university campus. One of our most significant aims is how the experience is throughout different years inside the campus. In this way, any user being the university component may re-experience the campus skyline of the student years and experience traveling in time inside a virtual world.

2. Experimental/Methodology/Design

METUVERSE (Middle East Technical University Universe) was created by the core team (23 active members). The team consists of five subgroups that create the system while the student clubs work on the missing fields of activity parallel to their current club activities. The subgroups are.

- Modeling Group
- Texture Design Group
- Game Development Group (UE5)
- Website Group
- Social Media Group

Each group works in coordination with each other and gradually carries out the activities and conveys their work to the other unit. Modeling Group models the whole 3D technical and non-technical models on the project. Some of the group members create objects on the same scale as reality, such as chairs, tables, doors, windows, and sculptures, by using Blender, Maya, and Sketchup. Other members of the Modelling Group, who are architecture undergraduate and graduate students, model the campus buildings adhering to bu-

Figure 6: METUVERSE the Faculty of Architecture Building view[17]

ilding plans on Rhino and Revit. In this process, the building plans mentioned have been collected from METU Construction Works and Technical Department (ODTÜ Yapı İşleri ve Teknik Daire Başkanlığı). It is worth emphasizing that campus buildings in METU are architecturally exceptional with unique features. This is because the Texture Design Group creates each digital texture on the project. These subgroup members initially analyze the building materials and patterns. Then, digital textures are created on Substance Designer and are exported as “.sbs”, “.sbrar”, and “.png” file formats. Some models are also checked on Substance Painter to test texture compatibility. All texture file formats, and all models are added to the project cloud file, Google Drive, by the creators, and then these are imported to the Unreal Engine 5 project by the Game Developer Group. All materials are put into the project file based on the historical timeline. This is because the project’s first building is the Faculty of Architecture structures and is ready for user experience.

METUVERSE will progress depending on reality to this extent; the documents regarding the process must be meticulously collected and examined. All data from various university units were shared with the project team to ensure that the whole process was realistic. In this process, technical building plans of all campus buildings over 3500 and the works on afforestation of the land, and over 200 photos of the construction processes of all buildings are collected from METU Construction Works and Technical Department (ODTÜ Yapı İşleri ve Teknik Daire Başkanlığı), METU Afforestation and Landscaping Directorate (ODTÜ Ağaçlandırma ve Çevre Düzenleme Müdürlüğü), and ODTÜBELLEK (METU Digital Library) respectively. A thesis [15], and research [16] were also collected and benefited from campus preservation research conduc-

Figure 7: Face Scanning Process [17]

ted by the METU Architecture Faculty. It ensured that the project was built by supporting academic data and archival documents.

An ideal metaverse must be integrated into WEB 3.0 and a blockchain background with a wallet system. Website Group members establish the project’s systemic connections through the mentioned infrastructures while establishing the project’s website. Social Media Group deals with promoting the project on social media platforms and interactions on these platforms.

The avatars of our projects have been selected by the teammates themselves, without the purchase from a market or made in a modeling program. The first avatar of the project is also Define, a member of the Game Developer Group. For the avatar creation process, the faces of the people and team members were scanned by LIDAR cameras. Revopoint 3D Scanner Pop-2 camera, used in this project, and the scan files are exported in “.ply” and “.jpeg” formats. The files should be transferred to the Unreal Engine 5 project in the second step, but the “.ply” format cannot be imported effectively. Hence, the files are initially opened on Blender, and then we can export the file as “.blend” from Blender. The avatar files can be imported on the game motor in this format and edited. As the third step, the file, edited on Unreal Engine 5, is transferred to Metahuman Creator, and we can edit the final avatar appearance, thereby changing details. Finally, the last document can be downloaded and added to the current Unreal Engine 5 project file.

For such a complex project to progress efficiently, more groups and activity lines are needed than the sub-groups mentioned. Hence, METUVERSE was also advancing by adhering to the university’s culture. In this process, it was decided to advance the project with

Figure 8: Faculty of Architecture Building in Real Life [17]

the help of a student society named METU Lifesaving and First Aid Society, and some METU Research Centers such as METU Disaster Management Implementation and Research Center, METU Audio-Visual Systems Research and Application Center.

3. Result and Discussion

In this project, efforts are made to solve problems such as distance education-communication, verification, and protection of academic documents by creating a realistic metaverse campus of Middle East Technical University (METU). During this process, the necessary technological developments were examined, and studies were carried out for developing and using these concepts. All data on university development were collected and archived under a single structure.

In the context of the project's timeline, the system became accessible for interactions. These interactions started not upon the completion of the entire campus modelling, but rather as the modeling of the campus continued. Thus, in parallel with the historical reality of the university campus, the system became accessible to university components. In this process, the Faculty of Architecture is the first building on campus, modeled based on the reality of the project and opened to interaction. However, the model was created to the same extent as it was built, not in its current form. In time, the renovation history of the building will be

Figure 9: Faculty of Architecture Building in METUVERSE [17]

examined, and the model will be updated. Unlike most metaverse projects around the world, METUVERSE is developing based on reality, so avatars are also scanned and modeled in parallel to the actual student faces at the university.

Also, the current hardware system needs to be improved to update the project with new faculty buildings and use multiplayer users effectively with computers or virtual reality glasses. After the necessary equipment is procured, the targeted features and plans will be added to the system gradually, such as importing building information of the structures to the models by using blockchain infrastructure, multiplayer activities, and NFT items to verify academic or non-academic documents.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we created an educational metaverse campus system to support the university's historical, architectural, and cultural background. From the architectural and engineering perspective, METUVERSE proposes a solution to use "Building Information Modelling (BIM) effectively inside the system with blockchain. In this way, the data, according to the university, may be used and accessed easily. It is the first digital twin metaverse campus project in Türkiye and one of the pioneers around the world. Besides, the university components can play and have realistic online communication for their academic, administrative, cultu-

ral, and social activities. While new technological developments, such as metaverse, blockchain, and virtual and augmented reality, can be improved by following more easily. All data on the university and campus land can be collected in a single structure, allowing it to be protected and used.

METUVERSE is a long-time project; today, the necessary infrastructure has been established to proceed following the specified conditions. Information about the university land and construction was collected from all units affiliated with the university and started to be used. Using this information, the campus's first faculty, the Faculty of Architecture, was modeled. Users could try the system within the model using virtual reality glasses or as a first or third person with a computer.

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Figure 10: A part of the METUVERSE Team (Credit: METUVERSE)